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To whom it may concern

This letter is to confirm that Andreas Happe, doctoral researcher in Business Informatics at TU Wien, supervised by Professor Juergen Cito, has approached the TU Wien Unit of Responsible Research Practices in order to address potential ethical questions concerning his research project with the working title *The Hacker's Mind*. Four independent peer reviewers reviewed the submitted proposal and discussed appropriate guidance in the meeting of the Pilot Research Ethics Committee.

The planned research will be conducted at TU Wien. A formal ethics approval body together with relevant structures at TU Wien are currently being conceptualized. It is, however, possible for any researcher or research team to voluntarily approach the *Pilot Research Ethics Committee (Pilot REC)* for *an informal research ethics peer review and guidance* from the perspective of research ethics. The focus of the Pilot REC is human research participation.

Andreas Happe's proposal was discussed in the Pilot REC meeting on July 8, 2022. The topics discussed included ethically relevant methodological clarifications, more specifically questions related to the involvement of voluntary human participants in the research as well as mitigating risk of contextual identification. The members of the Pilot REC provided a number of recommendations to address the potential concerns.

Andreas Happe appreciated the comments and recommendations provided as well as the time taken to discuss his proposal. The researcher is aware that he can approach the Pilot REC for further peer review, dialogue and guidance at any point in time during the course of his research project.

Submitting a proposal for peer review by the TU Wien Pilot REC is voluntary and the meeting and/or its documentation, such as this statement, do not constitute formal research ethical approval.

On behalf of the Pilot Research Ethics Committee,

Marjo Rauhala
Head of Service Unit of Responsible Research Practices

